
ENGLISH ROMANTICISM AND ITS DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This article aims at giving an overview on the whole romantic period. The start of the romantic period, the way it happened, the poets that helped to make this period shine, the background of the poets and the details of the romantic poetry that ruled this era – all of the aspects are described very elaborately in this article. The romantic age was established at the end of the eighteenth century and it lasted up to the 30's of the nineteenth century. This romantic period replaced the neoclassical period where the classical poets like Alexander Pope made classical poetry famous among readers.

Keywords: Romantic period, The development of English Romanticism, collaborative work, simplicity of everyday life, romantic ideology, neoclassical poetry, individual experience, intellectual sensibilities.

INTRODUCTION

The English Romantic movement, spanning from the late 18th to the early 19th centuries, was a revolutionary period in literary history characterized by a profound shift in artistic and philosophical sensibilities. Romanticism emerged as a reaction against the rationalism and order of the preceding Enlightenment era, seeking to emphasize individual expression, emotional intensity, and a deep connection to nature. One of the key features of English Romanticism was the celebration of the imagination as a source of creativity and inspiration. Romantic poets and writers sought to explore the depths of human emotion, often delving into themes of love, beauty, passion, and the supernatural. They valued spontaneity, intuition, and the subjective experience of the individual over the

constraints of reason and tradition. Nature also played a central role in the Romantic ideology, serving as a symbol of spiritual truth and an embodiment of the sublime. Poets like William Wordsworth and John Keats, among others, frequently used nature imagery to convey profound emotions and universal truths, highlighting the interconnectedness of the natural world with human consciousness.

MAIN BODY

The development of English Romanticism can be traced through the works of prominent poets such as William Blake, Samuel Taylor Coleridge, Lord Byron, Percy Bysshe Shelley, and Mary Shelley. Each of these writers contributed unique perspectives and styles to the movement, exploring themes of revolution, freedom, idealism, and the power of the human spirit. Overall, English Romanticism marked a significant departure from the intellectual and artistic norms of the past, ushering in a new era of creativity, individualism, and emotional expression in literature and the arts. Its influence can still be felt today in various forms of artistic expression and continues to captivate audiences with its timeless themes and rich imagery. English Romanticism, a movement that flourished in the late 18th and early 19th centuries, was a pivotal period in the history of literature characterized by a profound shift in artistic and intellectual sensibilities. This literary movement was a reaction to the rationalism and industrialization of the Enlightenment, emphasizing the importance of emotion, imagination, and the individual experience. The development of English Romanticism can be traced back to the end of the 18th century when poets like William Wordsworth and Samuel Taylor Coleridge published their collaborative work, "Lyrical Ballads" in 1798. This collection marked a departure from the formal and rigid structure of neoclassical poetry, introducing a new style that focused on everyday language, emotions, and the beauty of nature. William Wordsworth, often regarded as one of the central figures of the Romantic movement, emphasized the power of nature as a source of spiritual renewal and inspiration. His poetry celebrated the ordinary and the

mundane, finding beauty in the simplicity of everyday life. Samuel Taylor Coleridge, on the other hand, delved into the realm of the supernatural and the imagination, exploring themes of the mysterious, the Gothic, and the unconscious mind. His poem "Kubla Khan" is a prime example of his fascination with exotic imagery and dreamlike landscapes. The Romantic period also saw the emergence of poets like John Keats and Percy Bysshe Shelley, who brought a deep sensitivity and lyrical quality to their verse. Keats' odes, such as "Ode to a Nightingale" and "Ode on a Grecian Urn," are renowned for their beauty and philosophical depth, exploring themes of beauty, mortality, and the nature of art. Percy Bysshe Shelley, known for his radical political views and lyrical intensity, addressed themes of social justice, individual freedom, and the power of the imagination in his works. His poems, such as "Ode to the West Wind" and "Ozymandias," continue to resonate with readers for their passionate language and visionary spirit.

CONCLUSION

English Romanticism was a movement that championed the power of emotion, imagination, and individual expression in literature. The development of Romanticism was shaped by a diverse group of poets who revolutionized the literary landscape of their time, leaving a lasting legacy that continues to inspire readers and writers to this day.

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